

Supporting Information to

High performance Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzers using catalyst-coated membranes with exceptionally redox-active Ni-O ligands

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SI 1 Fundamental electrochemical evaluation of the catalyst activity and stability with a RDE setup

For electrocatalytic activity testing, a catalyst suspension was prepared. The suspension consists of 4 mg catalyst, 768 μL *i*-PrOH, 200 μL DI water and 32 μL 5 wt. % Nafion perfluorinated resin solution (Sigma Aldrich). 10 μL of the resulting catalyst dispersion was pipetted on the GC electrode (0.1963 cm^2) to reach an overall loading of 200 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The loadings were adjusted. The electro-catalytic performance of the catalyst was evaluated in N_2 -saturated 0.1 M and 1 M KOH at 1600 rpm using a Biologic SP-200 potentiostat operating in a three-electrode setup with a platinum counter electrode (CE) and a reversible hydrogen (RHE) reference electrode. All reported CVs are *i*R corrected. The overpotentials reported, necessary to reach a current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} (OER) are the average of three measurements. To test the stability of different types of ionomers during electrochemical strain 2000 CVs in a certain potential range were recorded (1.23 V vs. RHE and 1.63 V vs. RHE). The overall time of stability cycling is 16 hrs. The detailed electrochemical protocols are given in the following tables, which summarize the activity (Table S 1) and stability (Table S 2:) protocol, respectively. Figure S 2 depicts the stability protocol based on cyclic voltammetry advanced (CVA) technique from the Biologic Software.

Table S 1: Protocol for the investigation of the electrochemical activity towards OER in RDE.

Step	Technique	Parameters
1.	CA	1.1 V vs. RHE, 10 minutes
2.	PEIS	1.1 V vs. RHE; 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
3.	CV	1.1 V vs. RHE – 1.7 V vs. RHE; 5 mV s^{-1} ; two cycles
4.	CV	1.1 V vs. RHE – 1.7 V vs. RHE; 50 mV s^{-1} ; 20 cycles
5.	CV	1.1 V vs. RHE – 1.7 V vs. RHE; 5 mV s^{-1} ; two cycles
6.	PEIS	1.1 V vs. RHE; 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
7.	CA	1.1 V vs. RHE; 10 minutes

CA: chronoamperometry, PEIS: potentiostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, CV: cyclic voltammetry, CA: chronoamperometry.

Figure S 1: Zoom-In of the NiFe , NiCo and NiMn LDH CV cycle 24 depicting the nickel redox features of each material in more detail. The measurements were conducted in 0.1 M KOH at 1600 rpm at RT.

Table S 2: Protocol for the investigation of the electrochemical stability of the applied materials in RDE.

Step	Technique	Parameters
1.	CA	1.1 V vs. RHE, 10 minutes
2.	PEIS	1.1 V vs. RHE; 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
3.	CVA	1.23 (1.43) V vs. RHE – 1.7 V vs. RHE; 100 mV s ⁻¹ ; 10 s at initial and final potential; 2000 cycles
4.	CV	1.1 V vs. RHE – 1.7 V vs. RHE; 50 mV s ⁻¹ ; two cycles
5.	PEIS	1.1 V vs. RHE; 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
6.	CA	1.1 V vs. RHE; 10 minutes
7.	CA	1.1 V vs. RHE; 10 minutes

CA: chronoamperometry, PEIS: potentiostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, CVA: cyclic voltammetry advanced, CV: cyclic voltammetry, CA: chronoamperometry.

Figure S 2: Plot of the CVA based stability protocol, CVAs were recorded between 1.23 V and 1.63 V vs. RHE and 1.43 V and 1.63 V vs. RHE with a potential hold of 10 s at initial and final potential. The measurements were recorded in N_2 degassed KOH solution at RT.

Figure S 3: AST measured between 1.23 V vs. RHE and 1.63 V vs. RHE. NiFe LDH in 0.1 M KOH a) and 1 M KOH c) and IrO_x in 0.1 M KOH b) and 1 M KOH d). The measurements were conducted at 1600 rpm, at RT.

Figure S 4: ASTs of NiMn LDH (a and c) and NiCo LDH (b and d) in 0.1 M KOH (a and b) and in 1 M KOH (c and d). The measurements were conducted at 1600 rpm at RT.

AST conducted with NiMn and NiCo LDH are depicted in SI (Figure S 4). Neither NiMn nor NiCo LDH show significant losses of electrochemical activity with respect to OER in 0.1 M KOH and 1 M KOH during the AST performed. However, the electrochemical activities of both materials (NiMn, NiCo LDH) do not represent any improvement in the electrochemical performance of an anode equipped with the respective material. Interestingly, the characteristic Ni oxidation feature remain visible, even though it declines during AST. Still the achieved OER currents decayed during AST. This might be, besides material loss, caused by nano-scale gas bubbles formed during OER at the catalyst surface, which were not removed by rotation decreasing the catalytically active surface area.

SI 2 Electrochemical evaluations of the interfacial capacitance and the electrochemical surface area (ECSA) with a RDE setup

For the determination of the ECSA (Electrochemical Surface Area), the same catalyst ink as prepared for the measurement of the electrochemical activity was used. The catalyst-ink consists of 4 mg catalyst, 768 μL *i*-PrOH, 200 μL DI water and 32 μL 5 wt. % Nafion perfluorinated resin solution (Sigma Aldrich). 10 μL of the resulting dispersion was pipetted on a GC electrode (0.1963 cm^2) to reach an overall loading of $200\text{ }\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. Two different approaches of determining the ECSA are compared. The first one uses certain applied current densities, while the second one applies certain potentials. The first one is referred to as GEIS-based (galvanostatic EIS) and the second one is PEIS-based. The applied electrochemical protocol for the GEIS-based determination of the ECSA is summarized in the following table (Table S 3), the protocol for the PEIS-based determination is summarized in Table S 4.

Table S 3: GEIS based protocol for the determination of the ECSA.

Step	Technique	Parameters
1.	CA	1.23 V vs. RHE, 10 minutes
2.	GEIS	5 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
3.	GEIS	10 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
4.	GEIS	15 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
5.	GEIS	20 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
6.	GEIS	25 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
7.	GEIS	30 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
8.	GEIS	35 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
9.	GEIS	40 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
10.	GEIS	45 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
11.	GEIS	50 μA , 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
12.	GEIS	1 mA, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
13.	GEIS	1.1 mA, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
14.	CA	1.23 V vs. RHE, 10 minutes

Supplemental discussion 2.1

For this study, two different approaches determining the ECSA using impedance spectroscopy measurements are described: galvanostatic and potentiostatic (GEIS (Table S4) and PEIS (Table S5), respectively). Usually, PEIS is applied in the potential region slightly above the Ni-redox feature, where C_a is expected to be constant or show negligible variations.¹⁻⁴ The resulting impedance spectra are then fit using an equivalent circuit and C_a is evaluated.^{3,4} Despite very successful application of PEIS for the determination of the ECSA, investigating different catalyst materials applying PEIS bears disadvantageous behavior regarding resulting and material dependent currents accompanied with severe differences of iR -corrected applied potentials. Since electrocatalytic OER currents of NiFe LDH exceed the respective performance of NiMn and NiCo LDH by far, completely different iR -corrected potentials are applied (Figure S 5a and b, Figure S 6a and b). Therefore, galvanostatic impedance spectroscopy (GEIS) was used, applying small faradaic currents as setpoints. Here, only slightly varying material-dependent potentials were necessary, supplying the currents. However, the difference in potentials are not significant and the iR -corrected potential region is comparable (Figure S 7a and b). Interestingly, NiMn LDH has the lowest overpotential at very low currents. Still, NiCo LDH and especially NiFe LDH require much lower overpotentials for higher current densities.

Table S 4: Electrochemical Protocol for the determination of the ECSA via an applied potential (PEIS-based).

Step	Technique	Parameters
1.	CA	1.23 V vs. RHE, 10 minutes
2.	PEIS	1.51 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
3.	PEIS	1.52 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
4.	PEIS	1.53 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
5.	PEIS	1.54 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
6.	PEIS	1.55 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
7.	PEIS	1.56 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
8.	PEIS	1.58 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
9.	PEIS	1.63 V vs. RHE, 1 MHz – 1.000 mHz
10.	CA	1.23 V vs. RHE, 10 minutes

The following figures summarize and complete the results of the impedance measurements.

Figure S 5: Resulting polarization curves of the PEIS measurements. A) NiCo (blue) and NiMn (red) and b) NiFe LDH (black). The measurements were conducted in N₂ saturated 0.1 M KOH at 1600 rpm and RT.

Figure S 6: PEIS based estimated charge of NiFe LDH, NiCo LDH and NiMn LDH. a) without iR-correction and b) with iR correction of the applied potential. The measurements were conducted in 0.1 M KOH at RT with a rotation rate of 1600 rpm.

As shown in the previous figures, the measurements of surface charges based on applied potentials lead to very similar results as before for measurements of surface charges based on applied currents. However, it should be noted that due to the different electrochemical activities and resulting currents, completely different potentials result from the iR correction performed. The currents measured for NiFe LDH are significantly higher than the currents measured for NiCo LDH and NiMn-LDH applying the same potential range, therefore the iR corrected potentials are significantly lower in the case of NiFe LDH and the resulting conditions under which the different catalysts were measured are different. Difference in applied potential between NiFe LDH and NiCo LDH or NiMn LDH is min 200 mV and max 1000 mV. This is depicted in Figure S 6a, b. The conditions used for the GEIS measurements are therefore much more comparable for the used materials (Figure S 7). Again, it is to mention, that despite the very different resulting current densities, charge densities remain comparable between NiFe LDH, NiCo LDH and NiMn LDH.

Figure S 7: GEIS based estimated charge of NiFe LDH, NiCo LDH and NiMn LDH. a) without iR-correction and b) with iR correction of the applied potential. The measurements were conducted in 0.1 M KOH at RT with a rotation rate of 1600 rpm.

SI 3 Set-up for operando X-ray absorption spectroscopy

Operando O K-edge XAS and Ni L-edge XAS were performed in total fluorescence yield (TFY) mode with the LiXEdrom setup at the soft X-ray beamline U49-2_PGM-1 at the synchrotron-radiation facility BESSY II, Berlin, Germany. Solutions of the respective LDH and Nafion® in *i*-PrOH and water (4 mg catalyst, 768 μ L *i*-PrOH, 200 μ L DI water, 32 μ L Nafion (5 wt. % solution in alcohol)) were dropcasted onto Au-coated SiN_x membranes. The LDH ink was applied onto the SiN_x membranes in 10 steps of 5 μ L with a minimum of 10 minutes of drying between each drop. The catalyst-coated membrane was inserted into an electrochemical flow cell designed by Tesch *et al.*,⁵ which was used for the electrochemical activation and for recording of operando TFY-XAS spectra. A scheme of the set-up is displayed in Figure S 8. The electrolyte, 0.1 M Fe-free KOH (previously purified following the procedure described by Trotochaud *et al.*,⁶ starting electrolyte: 30 wt.% NaOH in water, Suprapur®), was pumped through the cell via a syringe pump at a rate of 50 μ L/min. A leak-free Ag/AgCl electrode (Innovative Instruments, Inc. LF-1.6, 3.4 M AgCl) was used as the reference electrode and a Pt-wire as counter electrode. The Au-layer on top of the SiN_x membranes served as the connection for the working electrode. Potentials were applied with a BioLogic potentiostat (SP-200, BioLogic Scientific Instruments). Prior to operando XAS measurements, the samples were treated by cycling 50 times between 1.15 and 1.85 V RHE at 50 mV/s. All spectra were normalized to the incoming photon flux.

Figure S 8: Schematic representation of the photoelectrochemical set-up and the X-ray interaction with the LDH through the photon-transparent SiN_x membrane.

SI 4 Potentiodynamic tracking of O and Ni features of NiCo and NiMn LDHs

Figure S 9: a) TFY signal at 528.7 eV as a function of potential recorded during cycling at 5 mV/s, derivatives of the TFY signal and the corresponding CV of NiCo LDH. b) Comparison of the spectral feature at 528.7 eV and the Ni(IV) signature at 856.2 eV for NiCo LDH. c) TFY signal at 528.7 eV as a function of potential recorded during cycling at 5 mV/s, derivatives of the TFY signal and the corresponding CV of NiMn LDH. d) Comparison of the spectral feature at 528.7 eV and the Ni(IV) signature at 856.2 eV for NiMn LDH.

To gain an element selective picture of the redox processes in NiCo and NiMn LDHs, we measured the total fluorescence yield at fixed energies, 528.7 and 856.2 eV, during cyclic voltammetry. Tracking the TFY intensity at 528.7 eV enables linking the occurrence of the oxygen species causing this absorption feature to the voltammetric response. Monitoring the absorption signal at 856.2 eV gives information about Ni⁴⁺ species in the sample, which is not accessible in such a distinct manner through electrochemical measurements.

In NiCo LDH, the oxidation wave in the CV, the point of inflection of the TFY signal at 528.7 eV and thus the peak of its derivative coincides at 1.25 V vs. RHE (marked by light red line in Figure S 9a). This reveals that the electrochemically observed Ni oxidation is directly correlated to the formation of the O-529 eV species as shown for NiFe LDH in the main text. From the direct comparison of the signal at 528.7 eV and the Ni⁴⁺ feature at 856.2 eV (Figure S 9b) it is apparent that the formation of O-529 eV oxygen sites and the Ni⁴⁺ redox occur at the exact same potentials since both curves are almost congruent.

We note that the signal-to-noise ratio for the NiMn LDH samples was too low to get unambiguous information on the potentials relevant for O-529 eV species formation (Figure S 9c). However, the comparison of the TFY signals at 528.7 and 856.2 eV (Figure S 9d)

confirms the same phenomenon that has been observed in NiFe and NiCo LDH: Concurrence of the presence of Ni^{4+} and O-529 eV species.

In Figure S 10a, the operando Ni L-edge spectra of NiFe LDH are compared to reference spectra of β - and γ -NiOOH. Notably, the spectrum at 1.45 V vs. RHE corresponds to that of γ -NiOOH. When a potential of 1.15 V vs. RHE is applied again, the initial intensity of the spectral features is reached confirming a reversible reduction to the α -NiFe LDH phase. Reversibility of the double-peak features is also given for NiCo and NiMn LDH (Figure S 10b-c).

Figure S 10: Operando Ni L-edge TFY absorption spectra of a) NiFe LDH, b) NiCo LDH and c) NiMn LDH at 1.15, 1.45, 1.85 and again 1.15 V vs. RHE. Reference spectra taken from ref^{7,8}.

SI 5 Correlating changes of the atomic and electronic structure during the α/γ -phase transition

Figure S 11 Correlating changes of the atomic and electronic structure during activation of NiFe LDH into the OER-active gamma-phase. a) Interlayer distance d in NiFe LDH obtained by fitting the (003) peak with Pseudo-Voigt functions during potential steps in an operando wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) experiment in 0.1 M KOH, after cyclic voltammetry

activation. Black arrow shows the direction of the 10 min potential steps during the time of experiment (results during the anodic potential direction are in red, cathodic direction in blue). At potential above 1.4 V two contributions are necessary to fit the peak (square and circle points), which remains and disappears when the potential decreased below 1.3 V (upwards and downwards triangles). Dashed lines at 7.8 and 7.2 Å show the interlayer distances for the α - and γ -NiFe LDH, respectively, as obtained by Rietveld refinement of selected potentials. Data for Figure a) are replotted and readapted from reference.⁹ b) TFY intensity at 528.7 eV as a function of potential. The grey graph represents the averaged result of five individual measurements (results during the anodic potential direction are in red, cathodic direction in blue; graphs were smoothed for better visibility), c) TFY intensity at 856.2 eV as a function of potential and d) corresponding current at a scan rate of 5 mV/s.

Supplemental Discussion 5.1

Our results from the potential tracking of the 528.7 eV feature in the O K-edge spectrum and the 856.2 eV feature in the Ni L-edge spectrum show evidence of changes in the catalyst's electronic structure that correlate with the redox features in the cyclic voltammetry. The electronic information can be correlated to structural information at the atomic and crystal structure level by using one or a combination of a few techniques, such as high-resolution X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD) or wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) and/or Fe or/and Ni K-edges extended X-ray absorption fine structure (EXAFS), or high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM). These relevant methods of structural characterization have been widely discussed in recent reviews.¹⁰⁻¹³ Such methodologies, more specifically operando WAXS in 0.1 M KOH, was adopted by the authors and the results published in reference.⁹ In Figure S 11a one of the results of that study has been readapted and replotted to be compared with the potential tracking of the 528.7 eV feature in the O K-edge (b) and the 856.2 eV in the Ni L-edge (c) and the redox features in the CV (d) reported in this study. Figure S 11a shows the interlayer distance d in NiFe LDH obtained by fitting the (003) peak with Pseudo-Voigt functions during potential steps in an operando wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) experiment in 0.1 M KOH, after cyclic voltammetry activation. At potentials below 1.4 V vs RHE one single pseudo-Voigt contribution is necessary to fit the (003) peak, and the result agree well with the distance obtained by Rietveld refinement for the as prepared α -NiFe LDH (dashed line at 7.8 Å). Above 1.4 V two pseudo-Voigt functions are needed to fit the peak: one showing a minor contraction of the remaining alpha phase (full phase conversion is not reached), the other attributing to the appearance of a new phase, the OER catalytically active γ -phase, as showing by the agreement of the fit result with the distance obtained by Rietveld refinement (dashed line at 7.2 Å). More detailed structural information is available in our previous work,^{9,14} including considerations on the lattice parameter a , corresponding to the metal-metal distance within the layers and on the size of coherently scattering crystallite domains. Comparison of the four panels in Figure S 11 shows how the formation of the γ -phase occurs at the same potentials as the intensity increase in the 528.7 eV feature in the O K-edge spectrum, the 856.2 eV feature in the Ni L-edge spectrum and the oxidation feature in the CV attributed to the oxidation of Ni(II) sites. The second pseudo-Voigt function is not necessary for the fit at potentials below 1.3 V vs RHE, where the system is returning reversibly to the initial state. Below this potential the γ -phase is reconverted to the α -phase. Also in this

case, this structural transformation occurs at the same potentials as the decrease in intensity of the two electronic signatures in the XAS experiments and during the reduction feature in the CV, corresponding to reduction of Ni sites to Ni(II). Therefore, in all three experiments, operando WAXS, operando XAS at O K-edge, operando XAS at Ni L-edge, we find a strong correlation and we find changes that follow the activation and reversible transformation of the α/γ -NiFe LDH as function of potential. This correlation between electronic and structural information supports our assignment of the electronic changes majorly to changes occurring in the activation of the α - to γ -NiFe LDH phase.

SI 6 Computational details

Computational methods

Self-consistent, periodic density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed with the projector augmented wave (PAW) method,^{15,16} as implemented in the Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP).¹⁷ To achieve a highly accurate description of strongly-correlated LDHs with weak interaction between layers, we employ an error alignment and error cancellation approach which was developed in our recent work.¹⁸ More specifically, this approach includes use of a Hubbard U term¹⁹ to correct for self-interaction errors in 3d transition metal cations, a van der Waals functional optPBE²⁰ to describe the weak interaction that occurs between layered materials, and intercalated water and ions between layers, and use of a water-based reference state for the calculations to avoid incorrect description of the gas phase O₂ reference with standard DFT-GGA methods. Its accuracy is demonstrated through redox and (de)hydration of Mn, Fe, Co and Ni based bulk oxides and (oxy)hydroxides with standard errors of 0.04 eV per reaction formula unit. Its performance on surface thermodynamics is also demonstrated in our recent work.^{9,14} U values, which are applied to d-orbitals of Fe, Co and Ni, are taken as 2.5 eV, 3.5 and 5.2 eV, respectively. A cutoff energy of 400 eV is employed. Monkhorst–Pack k-point grids (4×3×1) are used for Brillouin zone integration. The equilibrium geometries are obtained when the maximum atomic forces are smaller than 0.01 eV/Å and when a total energy convergence of 10⁻⁵ eV is achieved for the electronic self-consistent field loop.

Figure S 12: Atomic structures of (a) α -NiX LDH and (b) γ -NiX LDH (X = Ni, Fe, Co, Mn). The stoichiometries are Ni₆X₂CO₃(OH)₁₆·4H₂O and Ni₆X₂K₂O₁₆·4H₂O, respectively. The interlayer distance and the in-plane lattice constant are ~7.8 Å and ~3.1 Å for α -NiX LDH; and ~7.2 Å and ~2.85 Å for γ -NiX LDH, respectively. The black lines indicate the unit cells.

The cell shape and volume bulk phases of α -NiX LDH and γ -NiX LDH (X = Ni, Fe, Co, Mn) have been studied in our previous works (see Figure S 12).^{9,14} Specifically, the stoichiometry of the

α phase is $\text{Ni}_6\text{X}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_{16}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which is composed of $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ layers intercalated with anion CO_3^{2-} and water molecules. The stoichiometry of the γ phase is $\text{Ni}_6\text{X}_2\text{K}_2\text{O}_{16}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which is composed of MO_2 layers intercalated with cation K^+ and water molecules. The α phase has an interlayer distance of $\sim 7.8 \text{ \AA}$ and an in-plane lattice constant of $\sim 3.1 \text{ \AA}$. The interlayer distance and in-plane lattice constant of the γ phase is about 8% smaller than that of the α phase, i.e., $\sim 7.2 \text{ \AA}$ and $\sim 2.85 \text{ \AA}$, respectively.

We used the (01-10) edge surface of both α - and γ -phases to investigate surface phase diagrams and OER mechanisms in our previous work.¹⁴ Based on our previous work, we know that all surface sites are fully saturated under OER conditions, i.e., undercoordinated metal sites are saturated by atop OH adsorption, and undercoordinated bridge O sites, if there are any, are saturated by H forming bridged OH (see Figure S 13).^{9,14} Such a steady-state surface configuration is denoted as OH(bri)+OH(top). ΔG of other surface configurations is referred to such as a configuration, which can be denoted as OH*. Specially, ΔG of the surface oxidation is defined as $\text{OH}^* \rightarrow \text{O}^* + \text{H}^+ + \text{e}^-$ and ΔG of the surface reduction is defined as $\text{OH}^* + \text{H}^+ + \text{e}^- \rightarrow * + \text{H}_2\text{O}$. * is a surface site or so-called surface vacancy (V).

In order to construct the phase diagram, we employed a so-called computational hydrogen electrode method²¹, i.e.,

It is in equilibrium at $U_{\text{SHE}}^0 = 0$ under standard condition (pH 0), i.e.,

$$\mu^0(\text{H}^+) + \mu^0(\text{e}^-) = \mu^0(\text{H}^+) - eU_{\text{SHE}}^0 = 0.5\mu^0(\text{H}_2)$$

At the other (U , pH) conditions,

$$\mu(\text{H}^+) - \mu(\text{e}^-) = 0.5\mu^0(\text{H}_2) + \Delta\mu(\text{H}^+ + \text{e}^-)$$

$$\Delta\mu(\text{H}^+ + \text{e}^-) = k_{\text{B}}T\ln(\alpha(\text{H}^+)) - e(U - U_{\text{SHE}}^0) = -k_{\text{B}}T\ln(10)\text{pH} - e(U - U_{\text{SHE}}^0)$$

Figure S 13: Atomic structures of the (01-10) edge surface of (a) α -NiX LDH and (b) γ -NiX LDH (X = Ni, Fe, Co, Mn). The black lines indicate the unit cell with 2×8 metal atoms.

The Gibbs free energy correction of adsorbates includes zero point energy (ZPE), enthalpy (δH) and entropy (TS), and solvation effect ($E_{\text{solvation}}$) corrections (listed in Table S5) according to $G = E_{\text{DFT}} + \text{ZPE} + \delta H - TS + E_{\text{solvation}}$. Thermodynamic correction is used in the free energy calculations. Zero point energies are calculated with experimental vibrational data in Ref.^{22,23}, the integrated heat capacity ($\delta H^{0 \rightarrow 298\text{K}}$) and entropy at 298.15 K are obtained from Ref.²⁴. For water, the entropy is calculated at 0.035 bar through $S = S_0 + k_B T \ln(p/p^0)$ to derive the chemical potential of liquid water, because at this pressure gas-phase water is in equilibrium with liquid water at 298.15 K. The solvation energies ($E_{\text{solvation}}$) are evaluated through *ab initio* molecular dynamics simulations by filling the vacuum with liquid water with a thickness that is equivalent to 5 water bilayers. It worth noting that, in comparison with our previous work,^{25,26} the solvation energy of surface OH is about 0.3 eV smaller, because of high OH density in the current case which leads to a very limited amount of hydrogen bonds formed with interface water.

Table S 5. Thermodynamic correction used in the free energy calculations. The table shows the values for the zero point energies (ZPE), integrated heat capacity ($\delta H^{0 \rightarrow 298\text{K}}$), entropy at 298.15 K (TS@298K) and the solvation energies ($E_{\text{solvation}}$).

	ZPE (eV)	$\delta H^{0 \rightarrow 298\text{K}}$ (eV)	TS@298K (eV)	$E_{\text{solvation}}$ (eV)
H ₂ O	0.56	0.1	0.68	
H ₂	0.27	0.09	0.41	
OOH*	0.47	0.05	0.08	-0.4
O*	0.07	0.03	0.05	0
OH*	0.39	0.03	0.03	-0.3

O K-edge spectra simulation

X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) simulation were performed with the projector augmented wave (PAW) method,^{15,16} as implemented in the Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP).¹⁷ The K-edge XAS simulations of individual oxygen atoms in the equilibrium geometric structure was performed by the supercell core-hole (SCH) method, with one full core hole. In XCH simulations, a constant Gaussian broadening (CH_SIGMA) of 0.5 eV was introduced, which corresponds to a FWHM of ~ 1.2 eV. We used the OH-saturated (01-10) edge surface of both α - and γ -phases to calculate the electronic features and K-edge spectra of oxygen atoms at atop sites (μ_1) and bridge sites (μ_2) on the surface, and hollow sites (μ_3) under the surface in this work. In the (2 \times 1) supercell employed, two metal atoms are on the surface (see Figure S 13), which has $a = 5.7$ Å, $b = 7.4$ Å, and $c = 35.6$ Å. We did the parametric analysis and confirmed that the supercell size is enough to reproduce the peak features at 529 eV and 531 eV in experiment (see Figure S 14 a). While the size of the supercell doesn't influence the peaks at high energy, it indeed influences the relative intensity and the precise location of the peaks at 529 eV and 531 eV. However, those differences in the relative intensity and the precise location don't alter the conclusion of the current work. The number of unoccupied orbitals (empty bands) used in the calculations are three times as many as that of occupied orbitals, i.e., $N_{\text{empty}}/N_{\text{occupied}} = 3$. To verify the convergency of the number of empty bands used in our calculations, we have tested a few additional ratios, i.e., 1 and 7 as shown in Figure S 14 b. We found $N_{\text{empty}}/N_{\text{occupied}} = 3$ can ensure the convergence of the conduction band in the relevant energy range, which is consistent with the conclusion drawn in previous work.²⁷ The test of the effect of PAW pseudopotentials on the simulated spectra was performed by using different POTCAR versions as shown in Figure S 14 c and d. We compared the simulated spectra by using the POTCAR version 5.4 to ones by using the POTCAR version 6.4, including the version constructed for GM calculations. We compared both an μ_3 -OH atom in α -NiFe and an μ_3 -O atom in γ -NiFe, i.e., two key oxygen species studied in the current work. For the simulated XAS of μ_3 -OH atom in α -NiFe, the differences in the peaks at 531 eV is negligible, though there are small differences in the intensity and location for the peaks at higher energy. For the simulated XAS of μ_3 -O atom in γ -NiFe, on the other hand, the differences are negligible for the peaks at high energy, but there are some differences in the relative intensity and the precise location for the peaks at 529 eV and 531 eV. However, those differences are not large enough to influence the conclusion of the current work. In the current work, we used POTCAR version 5.4. We followed a previously reported procedure in the energy alignment.²⁸ Specially, we performed alignment once and only once with a known experienceable reference, i.e., the 531.3 peak of the alpha phase in the current work. Such a choice gives a constant Δ_{expt} value of -3.2 eV. All other simulated XANES were aligned relative to this constant value.

Figure S 14: a) Effect of the supercell size on the spectra shape of an $\mu_3\text{-O}$ atom in $\gamma\text{-NiFe}$ LDH. b) Effect of the number of empty bands on the spectra shape of an $\mu_3\text{-O}$ atom in $\gamma\text{-NiFe}$ LDH. Effect of the versions of PAW pseudopotentials on the spectra shape of (c) an $\mu_3\text{-OH}$ atom in $\alpha\text{-NiFe}$ LDH and (d) an $\mu_3\text{-O}$ atom in $\gamma\text{-NiFe}$ LDH.

O K-edge spectra broadening

In XAS, both Gaussian and Lorentzian broadening techniques are used to simulate or fit experimental data due to their ability to accurately represent different physical phenomena affecting the line shape of spectral features. In the current work mentioned above, a constant Gaussian broadening (CH_SIGMA) of 0.5 eV was introduced, which corresponds to a FWHM of ~ 1.2 eV (see Eq.2). The VASP package only provides the Gaussian broadening, which is characterized by a symmetric bell-shaped curve and is primarily used to represent the effects of instrument broadening. Lorentzian broadening, on the other hand, has heavier tails compared to a Gaussian and is used to model core-hole lifetime broadening, which is missing in the VASP package. To verify the convergency of such a default parameter, we further conducted both Gaussian broadening and Lorentzian broadening in the post-processing as shown in Figure S 15. We first performed calculations with a small Gaussian broadening (SIGMA = 0.1 eV) in VASP to find the stick peaks, and then proceeded the post-processing with the Gaussians and/or Lorentzian function as shown in Eqs.1-4.

For the post-processing of Gaussian broadening, the parameter is the same as that used in VASP, i.e., SIGMA = 0.5 eV and FWHM = ~ 1.2 eV. For the post-processing of Lorentzian broadening, we used a similar parameter, i.e., GAMMA = 0.6 eV, which corresponds to FWHM = 1.2 eV. We further included both Gaussian broadening and Lorentzian broadening with the above parameters (Figure S 15). We can see that while differences in broadening may influence some details of simulated XAS, there are little effects on the relative intensity and the precise location of the peaks at 529 eV and 531 eV, which are key interests of the current

work. So, we conclude that the Gaussian broadening used in the current work is convergent enough.

$$I_{\text{Gaussian}} = I_{\text{Peak}} \times e^{-\frac{(E-E_{\text{Peak}})^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

$$\text{FWHM} = 2\sqrt{2\text{Ln}(2)}\sigma \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

$$I_{\text{Lorentzian}} = I_{\text{Peak}} \times \frac{1}{\pi} \times \frac{\gamma}{(E-E_{\text{Peak}})^2 + \gamma^2} \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

$$\text{FWHM} = 2\gamma \quad \text{Eq.4}$$

Figure S 15. Effect of broadening methods on the spectra shape of an $\mu_3\text{-O}$ atom in $\gamma\text{-NiFe}$ LDH.

Calculated XAS results

Figure S 16: Computational O K-edge of α -NiFe LDH edge surface, a) side view and b) front view of the atomic structure of α -NiFe LDH edge surface saturated by OH, with CO_3^{2-} ions intercalated into interlayers. Color code of Fe, Ni, O, H and C atoms are gold, gray, red, white, and brown, respectively. c) Calculated O K-edge of the oxygen atoms marked by number in a) and b).

Figure S 17: Computational O K-edge of γ -NiCo and γ -NiMn LDH edge surface. a-b) Average O K-edge of all oxygen atoms at the hollow sites of α and γ phases, and the combination of various α/γ ratios of 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 0.9, respectively. All curves are normalized by the maximal values in energy range around 531 eV. c-d) Computational O K-edge of an individual oxygen atom at the bridge site in different OER intermediate OH^* , O^* , and OOH^* , and the combination of various OH^*/O^* and O^*/OOH^* ratios of 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, and 0.9, respectively. All curves are normalized by the maximal values near the main peak (around 540 eV, among these range, all curves are almost identical).

Supplemental Discussion 6.1

In an effort to learn more about the electronic characteristics of reactive O ligands of NiFe LDH catalysts during OER condition, we used γ -NiFe LDH (01-10) edge surface as an example to investigate the electronic features of oxygen atoms in various local environments. The steady-state surface of γ -NiFe LDH (01-10) saturated by OH (marked as OH*) during OER was determined by the surface diagram in **Error! Reference source not found.**. Two OH at bridge sites both oxidized to O* (marked as bri-O*) can only occur at a high potential over 1.6 V, accompanied by $\text{Ni}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Ni}^{4+}$ and $\text{Fe}^{4+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{5+}$. The deeply oxidized surface with two OH at atop sites also both oxidized to O* (marked as all-O*) exists at higher potential, over 2.2 V, where Ni and Fe atoms remain in the oxidation state +4 and +5, respectively. By analysis of metal redox during surface oxidation, we found that the preferential oxidation of OH happens at the bridge sites, accompanied by the Ni oxidation and unchanged O magnetic moments of zero, indicating its strong covalency. On the deeply oxidized surface, surface Ni^{4+} and Fe^{5+} atoms are hard to oxidize further. And then oxygen atoms, especially at the atop sites are oxidized, of which the magnetic moments are 0.5-1.1 μ_B and the oxidation states are higher than -2 to form $\text{O}^{(\text{II}-\delta)-}$ in **Error! Reference source not found.**. These oxygen atoms with magnetic moments larger than 0.5 μ_B are more electron-deficient, of which the calculated O K-edge curves show an emerging peak at 528 eV.

Figure S 17: Surface structures and surface diagrams of γ -NiFe LDH (01-10) edge surface. The magnetic moments of Ni and Fe atoms on surfaces are given on the bottom in a), and corresponding metal oxidation states, which are deduced based on the intrinsic magnetic moments.

Figure S18: Surface structures and calculated O K-edge of γ -NiFe LDH (01-10) edge surface. a) Surface structure saturated with OH during OER (marked as OH* in surface diagram in **Error! Reference source not found.**). b) Surface structure with deep oxidation at high overpotential over 2.0 V (marked as O*(atop)+O*(bri) in surface diagram in **Error! Reference source not found.** 17). The magnetic moments of oxygen atoms at atop and bridge sites on surfaces are given on the corresponding oxygen atoms in a) and b). c) Calculated O K-edge of the oxygen atoms. The color code of lines in a) is consistent with that of oxygen atoms in a) and b). The oxygen atoms with identical geometric coordination and atomic magnetic moments shows the similar calculated K-edge. Only one representative O K-edge of one-type oxygen distinguished by color is presented in c).

SI 7 AEMWE measurements

Materials

Anion-exchange membrane (AP2-HNN8-X-50, Lot 2117L04) and anion-exchange ionomer (Aemion⁺ AP2-HNN6-00-X, Lot JMY191201, and AP2-HNN8-00-X, Lot JMY200701¹) were provided by Ionomr Innovations Inc. NiFe LDH (this work) and Pt/C (50 wt%, Umicore, Elyst Pt50 0550 – 3000110038) were used as catalysts. MeOH ($\geq 99,9\%$) was purchased from Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG. Potassium hydroxide (KOH) pellets (85%, VWR) were used to prepare KOH solutions. Nickel fiber felts (0.2 mm) were purchased from Bekaert and Freudenberg H24C5 carbon paper with a microporous layer was purchased from The Fuel Cell Store. PTFE sheets were purchased from Böhme-Kunststofftechnik GmbH & Co. KG as gasket, spacer, and casting substrate materials. ZrO₂ grinding balls (Retsch, 5mm, 22.455.0009) were used for ink mixing.

Membrane electrode assembly (MEA) preparation

MEAs with active area of 5 cm² comprising a catalyst coated membrane (CCM), Nickel felts as an anode porous transport layer (PTL), carbon paper with a microporous layer as a cathode PTL and two PTFE gaskets encompassing both PTLs. The setup is presented in detail in Figure S 19.

Cathode inks consisting of Pt/C 50 (0.3 g), deionized H₂O (1.8 g) and Aemion⁺ solution (2.5 wt%, 1.8 g) were combined in a 20 mL glass vial. After adding ZrO₂ grinding balls, the vials were left on a roller mixer (IKA, ROLLER 10 digital, 0004013000) for two days at 80 rpm. For the anode-ink, NiFe LDH (0.3 g) was treated with water (0.9 g), a mixture of MeOH: H₂O (10:1, 0.45 g) and Aemion⁺ solution (5 wt%, 0.45 g) in MeOH:H₂O (10:1) in a 10 mL glass vial. After adding ZrO₂ grinding balls, the vials were left on a roller mixer for two days at 80 rpm. In case of NiFe LDH-inks, variations in viscosity were observed. Undesirable high viscosities were counteracted by the addition of small amounts of MeOH/H₂O (*eg.* 150 μ L) followed by a brief vigorous mixing using a vortex device (Scientific Industries, Vortex Genie 2). CCMs were fabricated by directly depositing the inks on the membrane (monolythic 50 μ m) via bar coating from both sides. After removing the back foil of the anode half CCM, the addition of an adhesive foil helped to minimize membrane swelling during the coating of the cathode catalyst layer as described by Koch & Metzler *et al.* in 2022.²⁹ The CCM is then ion-exchanged and then sandwiched between the PTFE gaskets and the PTLs, the MEA is compressed between two Au-coated Ti-flow fields with parallel flow direction, before being assembled between two PEEK plates using alignment rods to avoid moving of the components during fixture tightening.

¹ The initial measurements at 60 °C and 80 °C was carried out with AP2 - HNN6 as a binder, later measurements were carried out with AP2-HNN8 as a binder (see). The change had no significant influence on the performance - polarization curves in Fig 4 (main text) are the result of 3 measurements each (where one of each temperature is made with HNN6). There was no specific reason - rather material availability and consequence of simultaneous developments in various MEA components.

Figure S 19: Assembled cell fixture, showing the MEA sandwiched between two gold plated titanium flow fields/current collectors.

Table S 6 Table indicating the characteristics of the manufactured CCMs.

sample#	Binder in anode catalyst layer	Anode loading (mg/cm ²)	Cathode loading (mg/cm ²)	Measurement temperature (°C)	Test protocol	Figure in Main Text
1	AP2-HNN6	1.29	0.5	60	polarization curve	4 a)
2	AP2-HNN6	1.17	0.52	80	polarization curve	4 a)
3	AP2-HNN8	1.08	0.42	60	polarization curve	4 a)
4	AP2-HNN8	1.00	0.49	60	polarization curve	4 a)
5	AP2-HNN8	0.85	0.54	60	polarization curve	4 a)
6	AP2-HNN8	0.93	0.42	80	polarization curve	4 a)
7	AP2-HNN8	1.06	0.47	80	polarization curve	4 a)
8	AP2-HNN8	0.65	0.39	60	constant current hold	4 b)
9	AP2-HNN8	0.55	0.41	80	constant current hold	4 b)

Anion-exchange membrane water electrolyzer measurements

All CCMs underwent ion exchange into the hydroxide form via soaking in 3 M KOH for 24 h followed by another 24 h in 1 M KOH solution. A potentiostat with 20 A current range (VSP300, BioLogic), was used to precondition the CCMs, to record polarization curves and measure their degradation rates. The measurement protocol is based on the one described in Koch *et al.*³⁰ Minor adjustments were made to the measurement protocol as follows: Cells were measured with 5 A/cm² and at 1 M KOH electrolyte concentration. During the preconditioning of the cells the applied voltages were reduced to 1 V, 1.4 V, 1.6 V, and 1.8 V to avoid surpassing the 20 A current range limit of the potentiostat at higher voltages. After polarization curves and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements the testing protocol was terminated or continued with mid-term degradation experiments. During these mid-term tests, the cell potential was recorded at a current of 1 A/cm² for up to 110 h.

X-Ray Fluorescence Microscopy

A Bruker M4 Tornado X-ray fluorescence microscope (μ XRF) was used to determine the approximate loading of the anode and cathode catalysts on the CCMs. The loading was extracted using the Bruker XMethod software, modeling the sample layers. Due to sensitivity of the instrument on the focal level, unevenness of the membranes and CCMs can introduce a systematic inaccuracy, which is mitigated by taking the average of multiple segments on the CCM surface, imaged in a grid with a point separation of 60 μ m. The error bars are given by the standard error of the mean.

SI 8 Synthesis of the applied NiX-LDH materials

NiFe LDH was synthesized in a solvothermal one-pot synthesis route using a microwave-assisted autoclave (Anton-Paar 300 Monowave) as described by Dresch and Klingenhof *et al.*^{31,32} Prepared aqueous precursor solutions consisting of 1200 μ L of 0.6 M Ni(OAc)₂·4 H₂O (Sigma Aldrich, 99.998% purity) and 180 μ L of 0.6 M Fe(NO₃)₃·9 H₂O (Alfa Aesar, 98% purity) were added to 6 mL of dimethylformamide (DMF, Sigma Aldrich) and subsequently stirred for 12 h. Subsequently, 8 mL of ultrapure water (>18 M Ω at room temperature) and 4 mL of additional DMF were added to the reaction mixture. The solution was then microwave-treated at 120°C for 60 min and followed by 30 min at 160°C. The final product was collected by centrifugation, then repetitively washed with ethanol and ultrapure water, and finally freeze-dried. In case of NiCo LDH and NiMn LDH, 0.6 M solutions of Cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate (Alfa Aesar, 98.0%) and Manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, >99.0%) were used instead of 0.6 M Fe(NO₃)₃·9 H₂O.

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